

THE EFFECT OF THE INJECTION OF COBRA VENOM ON THE ASCORBIC ACID CONTENT OF DIFFERENT TISSUES OF THE GUINEA-PIG.

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Injection of cobra venom into guinea-pigs has been found to cause a depletion in the ascorbic acid content of brain, liver, adrenal, kidney and small intestine of guinea-pigs. The spleen is unaffected.

It has been observed that injection of diphtheria toxin causes an appreciable decrease in the vitamin C content of the tissues like adrenal, liver and kidney of guinea-pigs (Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 241; Lyman and King, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1936, **56**, 209; Harris, Passmore and Pagel, *Lancet*, 1937, **233**, 183). The administration of different drugs like atophan, quinine, arsenobenzene and poisons like phosphorus (Borselti, *Bull. Soc. Ital. Biol. Sper.*, 1938, **13**, 248; Wullner, *Munch. Med. Woch.*, 1938, **185**, 1785; Karolyi, *Orv. Hetil.*, 1938, **82**, 829; Ryang, *Trans. Soc. Path. Japan*, 1938, **28**, 486; *Nutritional Abstracts*, 1939, **8**, 646) have also been found to cause a reduction in tissue ascorbic acid. The present work was undertaken to investigate the effect of cobra venom on the vitamin C content of the tissues of the guinea-pig.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Male guinea-pigs weighing between 300 and 350 g. were fed on a normal diet of germinated gram and green grass *ad lib*.

Minimum Lethal Dose.—The minimum lethal dose (M.L.D.) for the animals was determined by injecting a weighed amount of cobra venom dissolved in normal saline, into the calf muscle of the hind leg of the animal. The dose which caused the death of 50% of the animals injected weighing between 300 and 350 g. within 24 to 48 hours was taken as the M.L.D.

The animals were killed by blowing air into their heart. As soon as the animal was dead tissues like brain, liver, adrenal, kidney, spleen and small intestine were separated and kept in a cold store (4°). They were taken in succession for the estimation of vitamin C.

The Method of Extraction of Ascorbic Acid from the Tissues.

Brain.—The whole of the brain tissue was taken in a glass mortar and was ground well. The minced tissues (2 g.) were weighed on a watch-

glass and were transferred into a mortar with a little sea-sand. 20% Trichloroacetic acid (2 c.c.) was added and the whole material was thoroughly ground. This was transferred to a 25 c.c. measuring cylinder and the volume was made up to 25 c.c. The solution was left to stand for a few minutes when the suspended particles settled to the bottom. The clear liquid at the top was filtered and taken for titration.

Liver.—The method employed was the same as for brain. The tissue (4 g.) was ground with 4 c.c. of 20% trichloroacetic acid and the final volume was made up to 50 c.c. and titrated.

Adrenal.—Both the adrenal glands of the animal were weighed and transferred to a mortar with sea-sand. 20% Trichloroacetic acid (1 c.c.) was added and the material extracted as before making up the volume to 20 c.c.

Kidney.—The whole kidney (1.5 g.) was taken with 2 c.c. of trichloroacetic acid. The volume was made up to 20 c.c.

Spleen.—The whole of the spleen was taken with 1 c.c. of trichloroacetic acid and the volume of the extract was adjusted at 20 c.c.

Small Intestine.—The small intestine (4 g.) was taken with 4 c.c. of trichloroacetic acid and treated as before. The final volume was made up to 50 c.c.

Estimation of Vitamin C.

The method of Sen-Gupta and Guha (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **16**, 547) was employed.

The tissue extracts obtained as above were titrated as quickly as possible against 0.1 c.c. of 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol (1 c.c. was equivalent to 0.104 mg. of ascorbic acid). An aliquot part (10 c.c.) of the tissue extract was taken in a flask and the p_H was adjusted to 5.6 by means of NaOH. 2 C.c. of an acetate buffer of the same p_H were added. Fresh cucumber juice was extracted, diluted 3 times and used as the source of ascorbic acid oxidase. The diluted juice (2 c.c.) was added and the mixture was incubated at 37° for half an hour. The volume was then made up to 15 c.c. and this was titrated against 2:6-dichlorophenol-indophenol. In control experiments the same sample of cucumber juice has been found to be entirely devoid of vitamin C before and after incubation and to be particularly rich in the oxidase. The difference between the initial titration value and the titration value obtained after oxidase treatment was taken as the measure of vitamin C.

Effect of Cobra Toxin.

In order to investigate the vitamin C content of the different tissues of guinea-pigs during cobra venom poisoning, $\frac{3}{4}$ M.L.D. of cobra venom was injected and the animal was killed 48 hours after the injection. The values for the ascorbic acid contents of different tissues are recorded in Table II. Similar estimation of vitamin C in different tissues was carried out with control animals which did not receive any cobra venom injection (Table I). Some animals received $\frac{1}{10}$ M.L.D. of cobra venom and were killed and the vitamin C content of the tissues was estimated (Table III).

TABLE I.

Ascorbic acid figures of normal control animals.

Serial No.	Body wt.	Ascorbic acid in mg. per g. of					Small intestine.
		Brain.	Liver.	Adrenal.	Kidney.	Spleen.	
1	333g.	0.074	0.050	0.450	0.069
2	318	0.076	0.050	0.440	0.066	0.095	0.074
3	315	0.074	0.053	0.430	0.061	0.150	0.076
4	312	0.072	0.054	0.460	0.059	0.147	0.072
5	324	0.079	0.051	0.426	0.057	0.153	0.074
6	324	0.076	0.050	0.586	0.051	0.146	0.079
	Mean	0.076	0.053	0.465	0.060	0.116	0.075

TABLE II.

Effect of single injection of $\frac{3}{4}$ M.L.D. of cobra venom at a time.

Animals were killed 48 hours after injection.

Serial No.	Body wt.	Ascorbic acid in mg. per g. of					Small intestine.
		Brain.	Liver.	Adrenal.	Kidney.	Spleen.	
1	325g.	0.064	0.043	0.240	0.045
2	325	0.041	0.044	0.280	0.044	0.118	0.044
3	327	0.065	0.046	0.413	0.051	0.120	0.055
4	335	0.063	0.045	0.386	0.045	0.082	0.050
5	345	0.063	0.036	0.260	0.052	0.120	0.062
6	345	0.059	0.036	0.260	0.055	0.118	0.060
	Mean	0.061	0.041	0.306	0.049	0.116	0.054

TABLE III.

Effect of 1/10 M.L.D. of cobra venom injected at a time.

Animals were killed 48 hours after the injection.

Serial No.	Body wt.	Ascorbic acid in mg. per g. of					Small intestine.
		Brain.	Liver.	Adrenal.	Kidney.	Spleen.	
1	335g.	0'072	0'041	0'460	0'049	0'151	0'069
2	329	0'067	0'052	0'520	0'054	0'183	0'063
3	322	0'070	0'055	0'458	0'048	0'126	0'065
4	330	0'070	0'043	0'447	0'048	0'090	0'065
	Mean	0'070	0'048	0'473	0'050	0'137	0'066

Tables I, II and III show that 48 hours after the injection of $\frac{3}{4}$ M.L.D. of venom, there is an appreciable decrease of vitamin C content of the different tissues. But the decrease was not so much when $\frac{1}{10}$ M.L.D. was injected. Ascorbic acid content of adrenal gland in the latter case did not decrease at all. It is of interest to note that the vitamin C content of spleen was not diminished either by $\frac{3}{4}$ or $\frac{1}{10}$ M.L.D. of cobra venom injection.

Detailed investigations were then carried out to find the effect of fractions of one M.L.D. of cobra venom injected on successive days on the ascorbic acid content of the tissues. Five groups of animals were used. The animals of one group received $\frac{1}{3}$ M.L.D. of the venom and were killed after 24 hours and the vitamin C content of the tissues was estimated. The second group received $\frac{1}{3}$ M.L.D. on two successive days and was killed on the 3rd day. The third group received $\frac{1}{3}$ M.L.D. on three successive days, thus receiving one full M.L.D. in all and was killed on the 4th day. The fourth group received one M.L.D. in one injection and was killed the next day. The fifth group acted as controls not receiving any venom injection, which gave a normal figure for tissue ascorbic acid. The results are given in Tables IV, V, VI, VII and VIII.

TABLE IV.

Effect of single Injection of 1/3 M.L.D. of cobra venom.

Animals were killed 24 hours after injection.

Serial No.	Body wt.	Ascorbic acid in mg. per g. of					Small intestine.
		Brain.	Liver.	Adrenal.	Kidney.		
1	315g.	0.058	0.042	0.265	0.032	0.053	
2	310	0.065	0.052	0.278	0.033	0.053	
3	320	0.065	0.050	0.257	0.036	0.062	
4	315	0.070	0.053	0.258	0.035	0.058	
5	322	0.063	0.052	0.316	0.038	0.057	
	Mean	0.064	0.050	0.274	0.034	0.057	

TABLE V.

Effect of 1/3 M.L.D. injected on two successive days.

Animals were killed on the 3rd day.

Serial No.	Body wt.	Ascorbic acid in mg. per g. of					Small intestine.
		Brain.	Liver.	Adrenal.	Kidney.		
1	350g.	0.053	0.042	0.204	0.032	0.052	
2	320	0.054	0.044	0.196	0.031	0.052	
3	315	0.063	0.052	0.205	0.036	0.052	
4.	312	0.067	0.047	0.261	0.033	0.053	
5	320	0.062	0.047	0.244	0.033	0.050	
6	330	0.059	0.046	0.210	0.035	0.062	
	Mean	0.050	0.047	0.220	0.033	0.053	

TABLE VI.

Effect of 1/3 M. L. D. injected on three successive days.

Animals were killed on the 4th day.

Serial No.	Body wt.	Ascorbic acid in mg. per g. of					Small intestine
		Brain.	Liver.	Adrenal.	Kidney.		
1	310g.	0.065	0.052	0.220	0.036	0.057	
2	315	0.063	0.053	0.270	0.034	0.055	
3	300	0.062	0.051	0.226	0.037	0.052	
4	312	0.057	0.050	0.263	0.036	0.052	
5	335	0.058	0.040	0.271	0.034	0.053	
6	325	0.062	0.045	0.289	0.033	0.052	
	Mean	0.061	0.048	0.257	0.035	0.053	

TABLE VII.

Effect of single injection of one full M.L.D.

Animals were killed on the next day when about to die.

Serial No.	Body wt.	Ascorbic acid in mg. per g of				
		Brain.	Liver.	Adrenal.	Kydney.	Small intestine
1	350g.	0.062	0.047	0.190	0.032	0.059
2	345	0.056	0.046	0.207	0.033	0.053
3	330	0.054	0.042	0.223	0.031	0.052
4	310	0.055	0.045	0.165	0.030	0.049
5	325	0.055	0.044	0.229	0.032	0.052
	Mean	0.057	0.042	0.206	0.032	0.053

TABLE VIII.

Ascorbic acid figures for normal animals.

Serial No.	Body wt.	Ascorbic acid in mg. per g. of				
		Brain.	Liver.	Adrenal	Kidney.	Small intestine.
1	352g.	0.076	0.055	0.431	0.052	0.068
2	345	0.070	0.053	0.406	0.048	0.076
3	325	0.068	0.051	0.353	0.040	0.070
4	310	0.074	0.053	0.324	0.045	0.067
5	335	0.071	0.052	0.364	0.046	0.069
6	342	0.073	0.054	0.367	0.043	0.072
	Mean	0.072	0.053	0.370	0.046	0.070

The mean values of the ascorbic acid recorded in the above tables are shown in relation to the varying doses of cobra venom injected in Fig. 1.

DISCUSSION.

Depletion of tissue ascorbic acid in guinea-pigs injected with diphtheria toxin has been investigated by various workers (*loc. cit.*). The present investigation shows similar depletion of vitamin C content of tissues like brain, liver, adrenal, kidney and small intestine as a result of the injection of the snake venom. The spleen, however, did not show any reduction in ascorbic acid content. Fig. 1 (dotted lines) shows that for all the tissues

the decrease of ascorbic acid content is maximum when a full M.L.D. is injected at one time ; in small intestine this maximum decrease is produced even by the injection of $1/3$ M.L.D.

FIG. 1.

B=Brain. I=Small intestine. L=Liver. K=Kidney. A=Adrenal gland.

The dotted lines indicate the reduction of ascorbic acid value in normal state to that obtained after a single injection of one full minimum lethal dose.

Ascorbic acid in γ (microgram) per g. of tissue. In the case of adrenal gland the value is expressed in $\text{mg} \times 10^{-2}$.

It will also be observed (Fig. 1) that the decrease in ascorbic acid values obtained after the injection of $1/3$ M.L.D. on two successive days is greater than that obtained after a single injection of $1/3$ M.L.D. But the values obtained after the injection of $1/3$ M.L.D. on three successive days are between the values obtained after a single injection of $1/3$ M.L.D.

and those obtained after two successive injections. These results would seem to indicate that the tissues try to raise their ascorbic acid content during mild intoxication.

It is of interest to investigate the fate of ascorbic acid which disappears and also the nature of the toxic constituent of the venom, which is responsible for causing this disappearance.

With animals receiving the same dose of venom it was observed that in these cases where outward symptoms of toxicity were very pronounced there was a smaller amount of ascorbic acid in the tissues, there was also a considerable hypertrophy of the adrenal gland, the gall bladder was full of bile, and the small intestine was congested with blood, whereas this occurred to a lesser extent in animals which showed less pronounced symptoms of toxicity. It is possible that in the former cases the venom prevents the flow of bile to a greater extent, which might have detoxicated the venom.

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